

Water Quality and Condition Monitoring 1 design report

prepared for

WP[3.4] – Water Quality and Condition Monitoring

Version: 3.0

Published: 2024-01-31

Approved by: Karol Leluk, Szymon Krawczuk PWR, SW Work Package Leader
Paul Zabel DLR Project Leader

List of Authors:

Participant No.	Short name	Author name(s)
1	DLR	
2	LSG	
3	TUBS	
4	SW	S. Krawczuk, D. Hornung, J. Orzechowski, A. Wojciechowicz
5	PWR	A. Cichoń, K. Leluk
6	TAS	

Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
1.0	2023-06-25	S. Krawczuk	First issue
2.0	2023-09-29	S. Krawczuk	Update of whole document
3.0	2024-01-31	S. Krawczuk, K. Leluk	Minor changes and updates, merged PWR and SW documents

Executive summary

Water Quality and Condition Monitoring is important part of the LUXEX project. That system was divided into 2 subsystems, 1 of which is the Scanway's LIBS system. The system uses laser, to turn little portion of water into plasma, which when it comes back to liquid form, emits light. Analysis of that light allows to get insight into what element were present in the sample – that is being realised by observing that light with spectrometer and analysing the spectral data. Whole system is being commended by its PC, which communicates with Data Acquisition System. The measurement are carried out on demand (trigger from DAQ) and the test result is later communicated back (OK/NOT OK). The results give qualitative information about what elements are present in the studied water.

Table of contents

Executive summary 3

Table of contents 4

1 Introduction 5

1.1 Applicable Documents..... 5

1.2 Reference Documents 5

1.3 Acronyms..... 5

2 Consolidated WQCM design description and justification 6

2.1 Concept of operation..... 6

3 Water Quality and Condition Monitoring 1 System Design 7

3.1 System context 7

3.2 System architecture..... 8

3.3 Optical system design and component selection 9

3.3.1 Selected laser 9

3.3.2 Gaussian beams 11

3.3.3 Measurement chamber 12

3.3.4 Emitting system – the laser and passive optics 14

3.3.5 Light collecting system..... 15

3.3.6 Spectrometer 16

3.4 PC..... 17

3.5 Software 18

3.6 Internal interfaces 18

3.6.1 Power interfaces 18

3.6.2 Internal data and control interfaces 19

3.7 CAD model 19

3.8 Laser safety..... 20

4 System’s external interfaces 21

4.1 Hydraulic interfaces..... 21

4.2 Data/command interfaces..... 21

4.2.1 Exchanged signals 21

4.2.2 Electrical characteristics of signals..... 21

4.3 Power interfaces..... 22

4.3.1 220V AC Power outlet..... 22

4.3.2 24V LUWEX power supply..... 22

5 Procurement, Assembly, Integration and Verification 23

5.1 Procurement..... 23

5.2 Assembly..... 23

5.3 Integration 23

5.4 Verification 23

5.4.1 Functional WQCM1 system level tests 23

5.4.2 Performance WQCM1 systems level tests 24

6 WQCM2 design description and justification..... 25

6.1 Concept of operation..... 25

6.2 Design description and justifications..... 25

6.2.1 Sensors..... 28

6.2.3 Electrical equipment 31

7 Electrical scheme 32

8 List of parts 33

9 CAD drawings..... 34

1 Introduction

This document, deliverable D3.6 for the LUXWEX project, describes the Water Quality and Condition Monitoring subsystem in relation to the in-line sensors provided by WUST. It contains the subsystem design, proposal and justification for selected solutions, and description of the subsystem operation and maintenance.

Quality and Condition Monitoring of water sourced from lunar ice-regolith simulant, or in the future, from ice in actual lunar regolith, is crucial for in-situ utilisation of lunar water. Without that, it is impossible to ensure whether the water meets potable and/or electrolysis purity requirements. In LUXWEX testing for quality was divided into two subsystems:

1. based on laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS) capable of detecting elements present in sample
2. using number of specialised probes to determine physical properties of water and concentration of some ions.

This document presents the detailed design of both of those systems, further referenced as *Water Quality and Condition Monitoring 1* (WQCM1) or *Scanway LIBS subsystem* (SW LIBS) and WQCM2 – PWR system. It was prepared as a deliverable for WP 3.4 “Subsystem Design and Manufacturing – Water Quality and Condition Monitoring. It is based on the earlier work completed in WP 2.3 “Preliminary System Design”.

1.1 Applicable Documents

n/a

1.2 Reference Documents

- | | |
|-------|---|
| [RD1] | D3.1 – Design definition and justification file |
| [RD2] | JUMO BlackLine conductivity sensor datasheet |
| [RD3] | JUMO ecoLine NTU turbidity sensor datasheet |
| [RD4] | JUMO tecLine pH electrodes datasheet |
| [RD5] | JUMO AQUIS touch P controller and transmitter datasheet |

1.3 Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
DACQ	Data Acquisition, Control and Power subsystem
LIBS	Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy
SW	Scanway
WPS	Water Purification and Storage subsystem
WQCM	Water Quality and Condition Monitoring subsystem
WUST	Wroclaw University of Science and Technology
WQCM1	Quality and Condition Monitoring 1 (Scanway’s part of Quality and Condition Monitoring System)
WQCM2	Quality and Condition Monitoring 1 (PWR part of Quality and Condition Monitoring System)
TAS	Thales Alenia Space
PC	Personal computer
PDU	Power distribution unit
CDR	Critical Design Review
PDR	Preliminary Design Review
AC	Alternating current
DAQ	Data Acquisition System
LIBS	Laser induced breakdown spectroscopy
AR	Anti-reflex
BK7	Type of glass

2 Consolidated WQCM design description and justification

2.1 Concept of operation

WQCM is designed for in-line monitoring of water quality within the WPS. In-line measurements include conductivity, turbidity and pH. For this purpose, a measurement module (PWR SENSORS) is designed that consists of the conductivity, turbidity and pH sensors, integrated with a dedicated transmitter placed on one plate. Two measurement modules are used within the WPS, the first module upstream (after MICRO-FILTRATION) and the second module downstream the WPS (after STORAGE III and after SWY LIBS). The location of the measurement modules (PWR SENSORS 1 and PWR SENSORS 2) is presented in the diagram below.

Figure 2-1: Block diagram of the overall system of the LUWEX experimental setup. Dashed arrows indicate signal and power interfaces. Solid arrows indicate water (solid, liquid or gaseous state) flow [RD1].

3 Water Quality and Condition Monitoring 1 System Design

3.1 System context

The system context is presented on figure 2-1. System is designed for the in-line measurement of water flowing through it, using LIBS technology. It is powered from the 220V AC supply. Commands and data are exchanged with data acquisition system. The measurement is carried out upon trigger and later the test result (ON/ NOT OK) is being returned. Raw measurement data and test results are being sent to database used by Scanway operating team. It is possible for operating team to update the software and system configuration over the internet. Detailed description of the system’s external interfaces can be found in chapter X.

Figure 3-1 System context diagram

System context is also presented together with system architecture on figure 3-2.

3.2 System architecture

System architecture is presented on the figure 3-2.

Figure 3-2 Internal architecture and system context of Quality and Condition Monitoring 1 system

Water flows into the system and out of the systems through fluidic connectors agreed with TAS and WUST. Valves present in the system possibly will be eliminated after tests prove the water analysis can be carried out without closing the valves. The measurement is to be performed within the *enclosed laser compartment*, so no laser light cannot exit to the space of the laboratory. Additionally, spiralled tubing is added to attenuate light that could theoretically exit from the *enclosed laser compartment* by means of tubing with water acting as optical fibre. *Measurement chamber* is an interface between laser, spectrometer and studied water. PC communicates with DLR *data acquisition system* and commands the operation of laser and spectrometer, as well as controls the *power distribution unit*. Laser status indicator lamp communicates the laser status, so everyone present in the lab knows whether it is armed and operating.

3.3 Optical system design and component selection

3.3.1 Selected laser

Main requirements for the laser are:

- to deliver energy high enough to turn water sample into plasma,
- to have wavelength compatible with spectrometer and allowing for analysis of spectra of elements of interest.

The laser selection was performed with help of laser manufacturers. Finally the CNI **LPS-1064-S** series was selected. Tests performed together with manufacturer proved that the laser with energy of 100 mJ is capable of turning steady water into plasma. Additional analyses proved its wavelength is sufficient to analyse elements of interest by means of selected spectrometer. Figures 2-2 and 2-3 present the some footage from the test. Considering the water flow rate, to ensure system reliability it was decided to select 300mJ version with high energy stability (<1% of laser energy between pulses).

Figure 3-3 Screenshot from the movie documenting the test of LPS-1064-s-100mJ laser with plasma spark clearly visible in the darkness, view from the side.

Figure 3-4 Photo of the test stand used to verify laser energy sufficiency, laser and its controller are not present on the photo.

Selected laser is class 4 laser device, what affects the system design as safety measures have to be included. Laser safety related aspects are described in chapter 3.8.

Laser subsystem consists of

- laser head,
- laser power supply,
- laser water chiller,
- laser status indicator lamp (not sold together with rest of laser subsystem elements).

Figure 3-5 Dimensions of laser, its controller/power supply and water chiller

3.3.2 Gaussian beams

Let’s assume, that LPS-1064 system produces ideal gaussian beam, which may be helpful during design of optical systems. Gaussian beam follows below equations:

$$w(z) = w_0 \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{z}{z_R}\right)^2}$$

$$R(z) = z + \frac{z_R^2}{z}$$

$$z_R = \frac{\pi w_0^2}{\lambda}$$

$$\theta = M^2 \frac{\lambda}{\pi w_0} = \frac{\theta}{2}$$

Where $w(z)$ s beam profile along z axis, which is also laser optical axis (assumption: beam is rotationally symmetric about z), w_0 is local minimum of $w(z)$ called beam waist, $R(z)$ is wavefront radius of curvature, z_R is Rayleigh range, where $R(z)$ is maximum, and λ is beam wavelength. M^2 is simply called “M squared factor” and it is a measure of quality of laser beam. In ideal gaussian beam, $M^2 = 1$.

In general, $M^2 \in (1; \infty)$; bigger M squared factor means worse quality of the beam. For ideal gaussian beam, waist and wavelength determines rest of the parameters. Figure below shows above in more suitable way.

Figure 3-6 Rotationally symmetric gaussian beam cross section, in the plane which consist laser optical axis z.

Table 3-1 shows beam parameters of the LPS-1064-S laser system. Black – from documentation or by definition, red – calculated from available parameters, assuming waist and wavelength.

Table 3-1 LPS-1064-S beam parameters vs gaussian beam parameters for the same wavelength and waist.

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Value (from datasheet)	Value (for ideal gaussian beam)
Beam waist	w_0	[mm]		3,25
Beam location	d_w	[mm]		100 – 200 outside
Wavelength	λ	[nm]		1064
Divergence	θ	[mrad]	1,50	0,11
M square factor	M^2	[]	12	1

3.3.3 Measurement chamber

Figures 3-7 and 3-8 shows general idea of the measurement technique. As can be seen, there are two sub-chambers, A – main chamber, and B – water chamber (CUVET FCTH23). Optical axes of emitting and collecting systems should be perpendicular to each other, to avoid inserting light directly from the emitting into collecting system. Thus figures are in both **XY** and **YZ** cross sections. Water pipes should not be parallel to the laser optical axis, to avoid light fibering through the pipes. Black arrow points the gravity force direction, blue arrows shows direction of water flow. Water plots are folded into spirals with highest curvature as possible, to reduce light fibering inside pipes.

Figure 3-7 Enclosed laser compartment with measurement chamber inside

Figure 3-8 Measurement chamber

Several methods were considered to capture the laser beam after passing through the water chamber:

Figure 3-9 1st concept of water chamber. XZ cross section.

Figure 3-10 2nd concept of water chamber. XZ cross section.

Figure 3-11 3rd concept of water chamber. XZ cross section.

The design that was assessed as the best is the top one on the fig. 3-9. Finally, a beam trap (Thorlabs BT610) was purchased.

3.3.4 Emitting system – the laser and passive optics

To form a plasma, which is needed in LIBS, laser beam needs to be focused inside the probe, thus inside the chamber with lunar water. Originally, waist of the laser beam produced by LPS-1064-S is located 10 – 20 cm away from the laser output, which might be too short. Another considering-worthy thing is that we might want to induce plasma in different places on the laser optical axis inside the chamber with lunar water. Mainly because of that two reasons, emitting systems should be equipped with beam-forming optics, which allows to control:

- beam waist,
- waist location,
- beam vergence.

Such a system consists probably of a single lens, which their relative displacement along laser optical axis result with change beam waist size and location. Figure 3-12 shows optical scheme of the emitting system and water chamber. Figure 3-13 shows water chamber with different smallest spot locations, caused by moving lens. Closing lens to the laser results in moving smallest spot size toward the laser.

Figure 3-12 Optical scheme with three different lens position. Colour of the rays represent, which lens is in use.

20 mm

Figure 3-13 Water chamber with different smallest spot locations. Closer look from figure 2-12.

In above design, lens is made with BK7, and windows of the water chamber – fused silica. This design is very initial, just to show main conception of the system. The more detailed designs assumes:

- Optical windows in the water chamber should be tilted to normal to the laser optical axis, to avoid any reflection of the beam back to the laser.
- Optical windows should be coated with AR.

3.3.5 Light collecting system

The system is designed to use Thorlabs RC12SMA-P01 element, which is off-axis paraboloidal mirror conjugated with fiber connector. Figure 3.14 shows photo of the RC12SMA element. Figure 3.15 shows optical simulation of the RC12SMA element.

Figure 3-14 RC12SMA element.

Figure 3-15 Optical layout of the mirror inside the RC12SMA element.

RC12SMA simply looks into the optical windows of measurement chamber and observed signal is then transmitted into connected optical fiber, that is connected to the viewing port of spectrometer.

Figures below shows Zemax model, interior of the laser chamber, and laser beam forming optical system.

Figure 3-16 Interior of the laser chamber scheme, including mechanical components and water flow system.

Figure 3-17 Laser beam forming optical system in two planes. From left: lens inside mounting, flow chamber, beam trap.

3.3.6 Spectrometer

Spectrometer is required to be able to identify elements of interest from spectra generated by laser with 1064nm wavelength. After evaluation of model spectra of those elements and comparing them to operational bands of available spectrometers, considering also price as secondary factor, initial choice was made to utilise ILT960 spectrometer. However, it turned out it lacked necessary software capabilities and considering control and data interface requirements, more expensive solution SR4 XR from Ocean optics and AR-YELLE 200 from Lasertechnik Berlin. Ultimately, the OCEAN-FX-XR1-ES spectrometer was chosen, which has a wavelength range from 300nm to 1000nm, which should be sufficient to recognize the substances present in the samples. It is a miniature spectrometer with improved connectivity and a built-in processing module based on the Cross Czerny-Turner design from Ocean Optics.

Considering the requirement 2.5.1 and 2.4.5, an analysis of expected spectra was made. Results – amplitude peaks for elements present in compounds that might be present in tested water, can be seen in the table below.

Table 3-2 Wavelengths for elements present in compounds of interest

Element	Wavelength 1	Wavelength 2	Wavelength 3	Wavelength 4	Wavelength 5	Wavelength 6	Wavelength 7
H	656	486	434	410	397	388	383
O	1126	928	843	824	778	719	701
	640	616	533	379	334	303	230
S (II)	1164	1141	1114	1064	1047	968	940
	925	888	866	793	774	745	717
	674	654	639	617	605	570	551
	469	416	402	-	-	-	-
N	1177	1127	1027	1055	1013	986	940
	903	863	821	746	648	383	-
C	1173	1070	941	910	247	193	165
	155	133	127	119	103	-	-
Si	288	251	212	185	153	126	119
Al	394	308	257	237	178	167	-
Ca	866	393	373	318	184	155	-
Fe	277	257	239	161	115	-	-
Ti	626	457	375	337	324	307	191
Mg	279	239	217	206	193	188	185
	154	-	-	-	-	-	-
S (IV)	1156	1115	1062	1043	968	944	919
	888	866	793	745	676	605	469
	402	332	210	178	166	148	143
	130	110	-	-	-	-	-
Mn	349	293	279	271	261	203	119
K	1178	1169	1103	958	765	403	-

The extreme wavelengths of peaks were for 103 nm and 1177 nm. Considering that each of the elements has a set of multiple peaks, it was decided that the 300 nm to 1000 nm shall be sufficient band for that project.

3.4 PC

Specification for the PC capable of reliable commanding of the subsystem operations, was based mostly on interface requirements (USB, RS232, Ethernet, at least 8 I/O lines). In order to limit the costs, specification was built partially on already owned components. The PC is designed to have two hard disk drive working in RAID 1 configuration in order to ensure data integrity.

Table 3-3 PC specification

PC component	Chosen model	Owned
Motherboard	AIMB-788	Yes
Processor	Intel Core i7-13700	Yes
RAM	M378A4G43AB2-CWE	No
Power supply	PS-460ATX-ZE	No
Housing	IPC-611MB	No
Drive	Gigabyte 512GB M.2 PCIe NVMe	No
I/O card	PCI-E-1730	No

The LIBS PC would be always powered on whenever the power is delivered to power subsystem, all other devices on/off state would be commanded by the LIBS PC by means of controlling the specific relay.

3.5 Software

The PC will run on Microsoft Windows system. Software will be developed mostly in Python. There are two main chunks of software that need to be developed:

1. QCM1 system control software,
(powering and configuring laser, powering and configuring the spectrometer, handling the communication with DAQ)
2. Data analysis software.
(interpretation of spectrometer measurements)

For data analysis, it is planned that tests will be performed to see the performance difference between algorithms prepared by spectroscopy manufacturer and our own solution based on machine learning.

3.6 Internal interfaces

3.6.1 Power interfaces

Table 3-4 WQCM1 power budget

No.	Powered device	Voltage rating	Peak Power	Mean power	Duty cycle	Power consumed per 1h
1.	LIBS PC	220V AC	800W	450W	100%	450 Wh
2.	Laser	220V AC	1000W	800W	30% TBD	240 Wh
3.	Spectrometer	5V	1,5W	1,5W	30% TBD	0,45 Wh
4.	Valve	24 V	TBD	TBD	0%	0 Wh
5.	Laser status indicator lamp	220V AC	60W	20W	100%	25 Wh

3.6.2 Internal data and control interfaces

Table 3-5 WQCM1 internal data and control interfaces

No.	Interfacing part A	Interfacing part B	Medium	Function
1.	LIBS PC	Spectrometer	USB	Powering the spectrometer, downloading spectral data
2.	LIBS PC	Laser	RS232	Control of laser operation
3.	LIBS PC	Valve	Voltage signal (high/low)	Opening and closing the valve
4.	LIBS PC	Power subsystem – laser relay	Voltage signal (high/low)	Tuning laser power on/off

3.7 CAD model

Figure 3-18 CAD model of WQCM1 - part 1

Figure 3-19 WQCM1 CAD model - part 2 (laser compartment)

3.8 Laser safety

Selected laser is classified as Class 4 laser device according to IEC 60825-1:2014 norm for safety of laser products. Described system is designed to meet the laser safety requirements as set by the abovementioned norm. The following measures to ensure operational safety of the system were taken:

1. The laser head operates within protective housing, preventing the laser beam from exiting into laboratory.
2. The internal surface of protective housing may be partially covered with Acktar foil, which has dampening attributes for the wavelength of chosen laser (1064nm).
3. The protective housing is designed to prevent its removal.
4. Removal of protective housing makes the laser inoperative.
5. Laser requires manual reset after its power is interrupted.
6. Laser is inoperative when its key is removed from its power supply.
7. Status lamp indicates the laser operation.
8. The device is to be labelled according to PN-EN 60825-1.

Additionally to those safety measures, set of safety glasses will be provided together with the system. They can be treated as an extra safety measure, as abovementioned solutions already limit the risk of laser light coming out of the enclosed laser compartment.

4 System’s external interfaces

4.1 Hydraulic interfaces

They are described in D3.1. chapter 3.1.

4.2 Data/command interfaces

That interface is described in details in D3.1 chapter 3.2.

4.2.1 Exchanged signals

Table below summarise the data/command lines existing between the WQCM1 and Data Acquisition System.

Table 4-1 Exchanged signals

No.	In/Out (LIBS PC perspective)	Signal type	Signal name	Information carried
1.	In	Logic flag	Trigger	High - measurement to be carried out in 30 TBD seconds
2.	Out	Logic flag	Laser powered on	High - Laser was activated and will fire within time window signaled by that signal
3.	Out	Logic flag	Valve closed	Physical feedback from valve control signal – valve normally open, high signal means that valve is closed (TBC)
4.	Out	Logic flag	Measurement OK	High – measurement finished; result is OK compared with specified requirements
5.	Out	Logic flag	Measurement not OK	High – measurement finished; result is NOT OK compared with specified requirements
6.	TBD	Logic flag	Placeholder	
7.	TBD	Logic flag	Placeholder	
8.	TBD	Logic flag	Placeholder	
9.	Power	Power	24 V	Power from DAQ
10.	Power	Power	GND	Power from DAQ

4.2.2 Electrical characteristics of signals

Exchanged signals are logical flags. True is signalled by connecting the communication line to 24V (supplied from DAQ) and false is signalled by connecting the communication line to GND.

High True 24 V

Low False GND

4.3 Power interfaces

Power interfaces are described in D3.1 chapter 3-2.

4.3.1 220V AC Power outlet

The system is designed to utilise 220 V AC to supply system components. The highest momentary power consumption is when the analysis is performed, when both laser and spectrometer are active, and is predicted to be no more than 2000 W. The power for the wall outlet will be distributed within the system by means of WQCM1 Power Distribution Unit. The power will be distributed to:

- PC,
- Laser power supply,
- Laser water chiller,
- Laser status indicator lamp.

4.3.2 24V LUXWEX power supply

24 V DC power supply coming from DAQ will be utilised for communication with DAQ and to control valve (if valve would be utilised). For now there is no other utilisation for it, but anyway we would like to keep connection to it in case it would be needed.

5 Procurement, Assembly, Integration and Verification

5.1 Procurement

Laser and spectrometer were identified as critical items from the perspective of the procurement, as that process in case of those may take longer. For both these items it is assumed, that they could be bought and delivered in two months from the closing date of CDR. Other items do not carry risk of postponing the project development due to procurement issues.

5.2 Assembly

Initially system will be assembled as a bench model after all of the components are delivered. Building a test support equipment simulating the water flow of parameters similar as assumed in real system is planned. After completing initial tests verifying the functionalities of the system, it will be assembled into its final form, after what final systems will be made, confirming that the system is ready for integration.

5.3 Integration

It is planned that system will be shipped for integration in disassembled or partially disassembled form. Assembly process and integration will be performed by Scanway personnel. The reason for shipping system in disassembled form is that assembled it would weight too much to be installed by 1 person. Integration is considered finished when final tests of systems operation are performed successfully. Integration is assumed to last ~6 hours.

5.4 Verification

5.4.1 Functional WQCM1 system level tests

Initial test plan has been developed. It is based on verifying the functionalities identified prior to and during system design development. Alternations to test dates were made, as due to late equipment delivery many of the tests could not be performed in their predefined time.

Table 5-1 Functional tests list

Test ID	What is being verified?	Status	Date
T1	Laser can turn water into plasma	Passed	August 23
T2	System is hydraulically tight		February 24
T3	LIBS PC can control the laser		February 24
T4	LIBC PC can control the spectrometer	Passed	December 23
T5	Spectrometer provides appropriate spectra		February 24
T6	LIBS PC can interpret spectrometer data		February 24
T7	Measurement can be triggered externally (by DAQ)		February 24
T8	Valve status is being communicated.		February 24
T9	Laser status is being communicated.		February 24
T10	Test result is being communicated.		February 24
T11	System can be operated remotely via internet.		February 24
T12	System software can be updated remotely.		February 24
T13	Measurement data are being saved locally and in		February 24

	cloud storage.		
T14	Housekeeping data is being saved locally and in cloud storage.		February 24

5.4.2 Performance WQCM1 systems level tests

Performance test will be carried out together with Wrocław University of Science and Technology. We plan to test both our systems using the same test solutions. Test solutions will be prepared by WUST. Exact specification of test solutions is yet being discussed. The test aim to prove proper functionality of both systems, to compare their performance and to evaluate possibility of acquiring quantitative data from LIBS instrument (designed to perform qualitative analysis in general).

6 WQCM2 design description and justification

6.1 Concept of operation

WQCM is designed for in-line monitoring of water quality within the WPS. In-line measurements include conductivity, turbidity and pH. For this purpose, a measurement module (PWR SENSORS) is designed that consists of the conductivity, turbidity and pH sensors, integrated with a dedicated transmitter placed on one plate. Two measurement modules are used within the WPS, the first module upstream (after MICRO-FILTRATION) and the second module downstream the WPS (after STORAGE III and after SWY LIBS). The location of the measurement modules (PWR SENSORS 1 and PWR SENSORS 2) is presented in the diagram below.

Figure 6-1: Block diagram of the overall system of the LUXWEX experimental setup. Dashed arrows indicate signal and power interfaces. Solid arrows indicate storage water (solid, liquid or gaseous state) flow [RD1].

6.2 Design description and justifications

The description and justification for the design features adopted in WQCM are given in table below. All design features are CE compliant.

Table 6-1: Description and justification for the WQCM design features

Design Feature	Justification
WQMC allows to monitor conductivity, turbidity and pH.	Conductivity provides information about the presence and concentration of ions in the water, while turbidity relates to the amount of suspended and colloidal particles. The measurement of pH can be used to verify conductivity measurements and to detect possible process impurities during the production and distribution of pure water. Simultaneous measurement of conductivity, turbidity and pH should be sufficient to determine water quality and identify potential anomalies in water treatment processes within WPS.

Design Feature	Justification
<p>WQCM consists of two measurement modules (PWR SENSORS), the first module upstream (after MICROFILTRATION) and the second module downstream the WPS (after STORAGE III and after SWY LIBS).</p> <p>Figure 6-2: Block diagram of the two PWR modules.</p>	<p>Placing PWR SENSORS at the beginning and end of the WPS allows to determine the degree of removal of pollutants from the water. Conductivity, turbidity and pH measurements are used as a monitoring and early warning system for potential WPS failures.</p> <p>In the case of irregularities recorded by the PWR SENSORS 2, it will be necessary to conduct a more detailed analysis of the composition of pollutants in the water, which will be performed using LIBS technology provided by SWY. The combination of conductivity, turbidity and pH measurements with the analysis of the elemental composition of contaminants in water provided by LIBS technology ensures full monitoring of water quality.</p>
<p>All components that make up the PWR SENSORS, i.e. sensors and transmitter, come from one manufacturer.</p>	<p>Using components from one manufacturer ensures compatibility of the system, simple assembly and operational reliability.</p>

Design Feature	Justification
<p>All components of PWR SENSORS, i.e. sensors, fittings and transmitter, are mounted on a perforated plate made of PP-H AlphaPlus®. Special holders are made compatible with the perforation of the plate, enabling the pipe and sensors to be attached to the plate in any position.</p> <p>PWR SENSORS are connected to the WPS process line with a flexible pipe (1/4'), equipped with connectors corresponding to the fittings used in the WPS.</p> <p>Total dimensions of a single PWR SENSORS are 40 x 40 x 15 cm.</p> <p>Total mass of a single PWR SENSORS is approx. 3.5 kg.</p>	<p>Two PWR SENSORS will be delivered as an integrated elements that can be connected to the WPS process line using a flexible pipe equipped with appropriate connectors. This allows for easy adaptation to the experimental setup, depending on the available space or integration with other elements and subsystems.</p>

Figure 6-3: Scheme of a single PWR SENSORS module.

Figure 6-4: 3-probe connection line.

6.2.1 Sensors

Table 6-2: Description and justification for the sensors design features

Design Feature	Justification
<p>JUMO Black Line Conductive 2-Electrode Conductivity Sensor 202922/20-0100-1003-60-104-20-5000-40/000 is used for conductivity monitoring.</p> <p>Figure 6-6: Conductivity sensor tech drawing [RD2].</p>	<p>Compact construction, with a fitting length of 40 mm the sensor can be screwed into pipeline with a small nominal diameter.</p> <p>The version with the cell constants $K = 1.0$ achieves a measuring range from 0.1 to 5mS/cm, which make it suitable for the measurement of either pure or contaminated water. Operating temperature: -5 to +80 °C, at 6 bar max pressure [RD2].</p>

Design Feature	Justification
<p>JUMO eco Line NTU Optical Sensor for Turbidity Measurements JUMO 202670/10-8-20-10/000 is used for turbidity monitoring. Dedicated flow fitting (JUMO part no. 00616715) is used for mounting the sensor on the process line.</p> <p>Figure 6-8: Turbidity sensor mounting [RD3].</p>	<p>The sensor is based on an infrared light measurement according to the 90° scattered light method (DIN EN ISO7027). Suitable for water quality monitoring with measuring range from 0 to 4000 NTU. Operating temperatures: -5 to +50 °C, at 5 bar max pressure.</p> <p>The JUMO eco Line NTU sensor stores its calibration data and history directly in the sensor electronics, meaning that it can be used quickly anywhere without the need for constant recalibration [RD3].</p>

Design Feature	Justification
<p>JUMO pH electrode in plastic shaft version type 201020/51-18-07-22-120/837 is used for pH monitoring. Dedicated pipe-insertion connector (JUMO 202822/105-062-26) is used for mounting the sensor on the process line.</p> <p>Figure 6-10: pH probe mounting [RD4].</p>	<p>JUMO electrodes for pH measurements are high-quality sensors for professional applications in process and industrial measurement technology.</p> <p>The sensors is equipped with a salt reserve, in the form of four salt rings. This is recommended when using the electrode in media with fewer ions or at high flow rates. The salt reserve helps to increase the service life of the electrode.</p> <p>Typical measuring range: 0 – 12 (briefly pH 14), operating temperatures: -5 to +80 °C at 10 bar (max. pressure) [RD4].</p>

6.2.3 Electrical equipment

Table 6-3: Electrical equipment design features description and justification

Design Feature	Justification
<p>JUMO AQUIS touch P type 202580/8-01-1-2-16-16-00-00-39-00/000/962 is used as a transmitter.</p> <p>Device setup</p> <p>(1) Mounting elements (2) Metal case barrel (3) Back panel with connection terminals (base unit and optional boards) (4) Case front</p> <p>(5) LED (voltage supply turned on) (6) Touchscreen TFT color monitor (7) USB interfaces</p> <p>Figure 6-11: Multichannel measuring device (front and rear) [RD5].</p>	<p>JUMO AQUIS touch P provides a central platform for the display and processing of conductivity, turbidity and pH values. Universal inputs can be used to measure almost any analog values using standard signals (4 to 20 mA or 0 to 10 V). The unit can measure and manage up to 23 parameters simultaneously.</p> <p>A paperless recorder is integrated for data recording. Up to 8 analog values and 6 binary signals are recorded and displayed on the screen in their chronological sequence. The data can be extracted via JUMO PCC software or USB flash drive and evaluated using the PC evaluation software JUMO PCA3000.</p> <p>Voltage supply for JUMO AQUIS touch P can be AC 110 to 240 V, 48 to 63 Hz or AC/DC 24 V +30/-25 %, 48 to 63 Hz. Maximum power consumption is 14.7 W at DC 24 V.</p> <p>The analog outputs from JUMO AQUIS touch P are freely scalable (current, voltage). Standard output signals are 0 to 10 V or 0(4) to 20 mA [RD5].</p>

7 Electrical scheme

Figure 7-1: Electrical scheme of WQCM

Table 7-1 Electrical interfaces for WQCM

Item	ID	Typology	Manufacturer	Part Number	Procured by	Notes
Line J6		Connection WROCLAW SENSORS 1 to DAQC				
PWR to DAQC jumper 6	J6	n/a	n/a	n/a	PWR	-
	E6.2.a	Circular MIL STD D38999 male, in-line electric connector, 26 PIN	Souriau	8D5-17W26PN	PWR	-
	JB	Junction box	EATON	n/a	PWR	-
DAQC wall mount connector	E6.2.b	Circular MIL STD D38999 female, panel mounted electric connector, 26 PIN	Souriau	8D0-17W26SN	DLR	Mates with 8D5-17W26PN

Table 7-2: Pin allocation for 8D517W26PN connector used in WQCM

Pin number	Pin description
pin 1	(+) PWR SENSORS 1 Conductivity 4-20 mA signal
pin 2	(-) PWR SENSORS 1 Conductivity 4-20 mA signal
pin 3	(+) PWR SENSORS 1 Turbidity 4-20 mA signal
pin 4	(-) PWR SENSORS 1 Turbidity 4-20 mA signal
pin 5	(+) PWR SENSORS 1 pH 4-20 mA signal
pin 6	(-) PWR SENSORS 1 pH 4-20 mA signal
pin 7	(+) PWR SENSORS 2 Conductivity 4-20 mA signal
pin 8	(-) PWR SENSORS 2 Conductivity 4-20 mA signal
pin 9	(+) PWR SENSORS 2 Turbidity 4-20 mA signal
pin 10	(-) PWR SENSORS 2 Turbidity 4-20 mA signal
pin 11	(+) PWR SENSORS 2 pH 4-20 mA signal
pin 12	(-) PWR SENSORS 2 pH 4-20 mA signal
pin 13	PWR SENSORS 1 Power supply 24V DC
pin 14	PWR SENSORS 2 Power supply 24V DC

8 List of parts

Table 8-1: List of parts in WQCM

No.	Element/Component	Qty	Manufacturer	Type
Sensors				
S01	Conductive 2-Electrode Conductivity Sensor	2	JUMO	202922/20-0100-1003-60-104-20-5000-40/000
S02	Optical Sensor for Turbidity Measurements	2	JUMO	202670/10-8-20-10/000
S03	pH electrode	2	JUMO	201020/51-18-07-22-120/837
Fittings				
F01	Male 1/4" PLC Series Connector	2	CPC	PLCD29004
F02	Flexible LLDPE tube 1/4"	4	John Guest	PE-08-BI-1000F-N
F03	Straight connector for 1/4" flexible tube (Series 1C) with male 3/8" G-thread	4	em-technik	1C100MG0338PP
F04	PVC-U reducing sleeve DN20 x 3/8"	4	GF+	721910434
F05	PVC-U straight tee 90° DN20 x 1/2"	2	GF+	721200206
F06	PVC-U DN50 x DN20 reduction	2	GF+	721900355
F07	PVC flow fitting for turbidity sensor DN50	2	JUMO	00616715
F08	PVC-U DN50 x DN40 reduction	2	GF+	721900352
F09	PVC-U straight tee 90° DN40 x DN20	2	GF+	721200155
F10	PVC-U DN40 x DN20 reduction	2	GF+	721900348
F11	Female 1/4" CPC QD self-locking	2	CPC	PLCD11004
Electrical equipment				
E01	Modular Multichannel Measuring Device for Liquid Analysis with Integrated Controller and Paperless Recorder	2	JUMO	202580/8-01-1-2-16-16-00-00-39-00/000/962
E02	Junction box	1	EATON	
E03	Circular MIL STD D38999 male, in-line electric connector, 26 PIN	1	EATON	8D517W26PN
E04	Cables	-	-	-
Others				
R01	Plate PP-H AlphaPlus® 40 x 30 x 15 cm	2	-	-
R02	KLIP-IT pipe holder type 061 PP	4	GF+	167061037
R03	Cable for pH sensor	2	JUMO	202990/02-92-1,5-13
R04	Pipe-insertion connector for pH sensor	2	JUMO	202822/105-062-26

9 CAD drawings

Figure 9-1: Single PWR SENSORS - overall view.

Figure 9-2: Single PWR SENSORS - top view and dimensions

Figure 9-3: Single PWR SENSORS - first side view and dimensions

Figure 9-4: Single PWR SENSORS - second side view and dimensions.

END OF DOCUMENT